

A Qualitative Comparison of Selected Automatic Depth Map Generators

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1 Introduction

The goal of the present report is to qualitatively compare the quality of depth maps generated by selected automatic depth map generators available at [3]. Focus is given on what are believed to be the four best automatic depth map generators, namely, DMAG2 [4] (an implementation of “Adaptive support-weight approach for correspondence search” by Yoon et al. [14]), DMAG5 [5] (an implementation of “Fast cost-volume filtering for visual correspondence and beyond” by Rhemann et al. [13]), DMAG6 [6] (“Efficient belief propagation for early vision” by Felzenszwalb et al. [11]), and DMAG7 [7] (an implementation of “Fast Bilateral-Space Stereo for Synthetic Defocus” by Barron et al. [2, 1, 10]). The comparison is purely qualitative, that is, it is based solely on what the depth maps obtained look like (no ground truth depth maps available). The stereo pairs used to generate the depth maps were all taken with an HTC Evo 3d cell phone (baseline is about 30 mm). They all have the same dimensions: 1920x1080 (two megapixels).

The first section briefly presents the methodology behind each of the automatic depth map generators that are gonna be tested as well as the parameters used. The second section shows the depth maps generated by each depth map generator for each stereo pair that was used in the testing. This reports ends with a discussion about the results and a comparison between the depth map generators is attempted.

2 The Players

2.1 DMAG2

DMAG2 is an implementation of “Adaptive support-weight approach for correspondence search” by Yoon et al. [14].

DMAG2 is a local method which relies on support windows to establish correspondences between pixels. In the support window centered at the pixel of interest, weights are given to pixels so that a pixel that is spatially close to and of similar color to the center pixel

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has a larger weight than one that is farther in space and/or that is dissimilar in color. The reasoning behind this is that one assumes that neighboring pixels of similar color are probably at the same depth, an assumption that is often made. These weights are actually the same weights that are used when convoluting a bilateral filter over an image.

The raw matching cost used in DMAG2 is defined by

$$cost = (1 - \alpha) \times cost_col + \alpha \times cost_grad$$

where

$$cost_col = \min\left(\frac{1}{3} \sum_{c=r,g,b} |I_c(x, y) - I_c(x - d, y)|, max_cost_col\right)$$

$$cost_grad = \min\left(\left|\frac{\partial I}{\partial x}(x, y) - \frac{\partial I}{\partial x}(x - d, y)\right|, max_cost_grad\right)$$

The parameter α (between 0 and 1) balances the color cost $cost_col$ and the gradient cost $cost_grad$. If the left and right images have not the same brightness and/or the hues are slightly different, it is better to rely on the gradient for the matching cost, which means bringing α closer to 1. I_c is the intensity for the rgb color channel c . The variable d is the disparity. The term max_cost_col is the maximum allowed color cost. The derivative $\frac{\partial I}{\partial x}$ is the gradient of the image (in grayscale mode) w/r to the x direction. The term max_cost_grad is the maximum allowed gradient cost.

DMAG2 computes a left and right depth map in order to detect questionable disparities (often referred as occlusions even if they may not all be) via the so-called left-right consistency check. The questionable disparities are replaced by more reliable disparities obtained from neighboring pixels which are then smoothed (using a bilateral filter).

Table 1 shows the parameters that were used to generate the depth maps for all the stereo pairs. “Radius” is the radius of the support window. The “alpha” in the table is the α in the formula above. The “truncation (color)” and “truncation (gradient)” in the table are the max_cost_col and max_cost_grad in the formula above, respectively. “Gamma proximity” and “gamma color” are the γ_p and the γ_c used in the paper, respectively. “Disparity tolerance” relates to the left-right consistency check. If set to 0, a strict left-right consistency is performed. “Radius (occlusions)”, “sigma space”, and “sigma color” control the inpainting of occluded pixels. The “downsampling factor” enables the speeding of the computations by downsampling the input images. If the “downsampling factor” is set to 1, the input images are used as is. If the “downsampling factor” is set to 2, the input images are downsampled by a factor of 2 (in each direction).

Downsampling was set to 2 when the disparity range was deemed too great. With a disparity range of about 40, DMAG2 runs in about 30 minutes on a run-of-the-mill linux computer with no downsampling (“downsampling factor” equal to 1). For any stereo pair with a range (much) greater than 40, DMAG2 was run with a “downsampling factor” equal to 2 in order not to go over the 30 minute running time.

Table 1: Parameters used with DMAG2.

	IMAG0013	IMAG0017	IMAG0019	IMAG020	IMAG026
Minimum disparity	-20	-72	-23	-20	-59
Maximum disparity	17	14	62	22	55
Radius	16	16	16	16	16
Alpha	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9
Truncation (color)	30	30	30	30	30
Truncation (gradient)	10	10	10	10	10
Gamma proximity	32	32	32	32	32
Gamma color	32	32	32	32	32
Disparity tolerance	0	0	0	0	0
Radius (occlusions)	9	9	9	9	9
Sigma space	9	9	9	9	9
Sigma color	25.5	25.5	25.5	25.5	25.5
Downsampling factor	1	2	2	1	2
	IMAG027	IMAG028	IMAG029	IMAG030	
Minimum disparity	-27	-19	-63	-31	
Maximum disparity	20	20	21	14	
Radius	16	16	16	16	
Alpha	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	
Truncation (color)	30	30	30	30	
Truncation (gradient)	10	10	10	10	
Gamma proximity	32	32	32	32	
Gamma color	32	32	32	32	
Disparity tolerance	0	0	0	0	
Radius (occlusions)	9	9	9	9	
Sigma space	9	9	9	9	
Sigma color	25.5	25.5	25.5	25.5	
Downsampling factor	1	1	2	1	

2.2 DMAG5

DMAG5 is an implementation of “Fast cost-volume filtering for visual correspondence and beyond” by Rhemann et al.” [13].

DMAG5 computes the (raw) cost volume, smoothes each slice with an edge preserving filter (similar to the bilateral filter in terms of functionality), and determines the best smoothed disparity for each pixel using a WTA (Winner Takes All) approach.

It should be noted that smoothing the raw matching cost using a support window and using WTA to get the best disparity (the one with the lowest cost) [what DMAG5 does] is equivalent to sliding (for every pixel) a support window along the scanline (between the minimum and maximum disparity), computing the weighted average cost at each station, and picking the disparity with the lowest weighted average cost [what DMAG2 does]. This important concept is further explained in [9].

The edge preserving filter used in DMAG5 is the so-called “guided filter” [12]. The advantage of the “guided filter” over the bilateral filter is that its running time is independent of the size of the kernel used.

DMAG5 uses the same raw matching cost as DMAG2. DMAG5 handles occlusions in the same way as DMAG2, that is, by computing a left and right depth map and using the left-right consistency check.

Table 2 shows the parameters that were used to generate the depth maps. “Radius” is the radius of the “guided filter” kernel. “Alpha”, “truncation (color)”, and “truncation (gradient)” are the same parameters used for DMAG2. The “epsilon” in the table relates to the “guided filter” regularization parameter ϵ of the paper by the formula $\epsilon = 255^2 \times 10^{-\text{epsilon}}$. “Disparity tolerance”, “radius (occlusions)”, “sigma space”, “sigma color”, and “downsampling factor” are the same parameters used for DMAG2.

Unlike DMAG2, DMAG5 is quite fast and the downsampling factor can be set to 1 without much concern. All test cases ran in about 3 minutes each.

Table 2: Parameters used with DMAG5.

	IMAG0013	IMAG0017	IMAG0019	IMAG0020	IMAG0026
Minimum disparity	-20	-72	-23	-20	-59
Maximum disparity	17	14	62	22	55
Radius	16	16	16	16	16
Alpha	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9
Truncation (color)	30	30	30	30	30
Truncation (gradient)	10	10	10	10	10
Epsilon	4	4	4	4	4
Disparity tolerance	0	0	0	0	0
Radius (occlusions)	9	9	9	9	9
Sigma space	9	9	9	9	9
Sigma color	25.5	25.5	25.5	25.5	25.5
Downsampling factor	1	1	1	1	1

	IMAG027	IMAG028	IMAG029	IMAG030
Minimum disparity	-27	-19	-63	-31
Maximum disparity	20	20	21	14
Radius	16	16	16	16
Alpha	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9
Truncation (color)	30	30	30	30
Truncation (gradient)	10	10	10	10
Epsilon	4	4	4	4
Disparity tolerance	0	0	0	0
Radius (occlusions)	9	9	9	9
Sigma space	9	9	9	9
Sigma color	25.5	25.5	25.5	25.5
Downsampling factor	1	1	1	1

2.3 DMAG6

DMAG6 is an implementation of “Efficient belief propagation for early vision” by Felzenszwalb et al. [11].

Unlike DMAG2 and DMAG5 which are local methods, DMAG6 is a global method. The problem of generating the depth map is posed as a minimization problem where the functional to minimize combines a raw matching cost and a smoothness cost which is summed up over all pixels. The smoothness cost is such that a neighboring pixel with a similar color and a similar depth (to the pixel under consideration) produces a lower cost than a neighboring pixel with a similar color and a different depth. The idea behind that smoothing cost is that neighboring pixels with similar color should be at the same depth, which is usually a reasonable assumption. Even though all global methods define similar functionals to minimize, they usually converge to different answers because there is not one single global minimum but many local minima.

To minimize that functional, which happens to be a NP-hard problem, DMAG6 uses a Belief Propagation (BP) approach that is been optimized for speed. Unfortunately, it has not been optimized for memory usage.

DMAG6 uses the same raw matching cost as DMAG2 and DMAG5. DMAG6 handles occlusions in the same way as DMAG2 and DMAG5, that is, by computing a left and right depth map and applying the left-right consistency check.

Table 3 shows the parameters that were used to generate the depth maps. “Alpha”, “truncation (color)”, and “truncation (gradient)” are the same parameters used for DMAG2 and DMAG5. The “truncation (discontinuity)” parameter which caps the discontinuity cost is set to something large (here, 10000) in order to disable it. In the paper, the discontinuity (smoothing) cost is defined as $V(f_p, f_q) = \min(|f_p - f_q|, d)$ where p is the pixel under consideration, q is a neighboring pixel, f_p is the disparity at p , f_q is the disparity at q , and d is the cap, the “truncation (discontinuity)” in the table. In all my tests, disabling the discontinuity cost cap works best. “Iteration number” controls the number of BP iterations within a given scale. “Level number” controls the number of scales in the BP multi-grid. The “data cost weight” is the weight given to the data cost in the functional that is minimized. The lower the weight, the more smooth the depth map will look (the less accurate too). “Disparity tolerance”, “radius (occlusions)”, “sigma space”, “sigma color”, and “downsampling factor” are the same parameters used for DMAG2 and DMAG5.

Because DMAG6 uses a lot of memory, setting the “downsampling factor” to 2 reduces the memory usage to a more reasonable amount. When the disparity range is about 40, DMAG6 consumes about 6 gigabytes of memory when processing at the finest scale. This is rather large so, for stereo pairs with more than 40 pixels of disparity range, the “downsampling factor” was set to 2 (just like what was done with DMAG2 but for speed reasons).

Table 3: Parameters used with DMAG6.

	IMAG0013	IMAG0017	IMAG0019	IMAG0020	IMAG0026
Minimum disparity	-20	-72	-23	-20	-59
Maximum disparity	17	14	62	22	55
Alpha	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9
Truncation (color)	30	30	30	30	30
Truncation (gradient)	10	10	10	10	10
Truncation (discontinuity)	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000
Iteration number	5	5	5	5	5
Level number	5	5	5	5	5
Data cost weight	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Disparity tolerance	0	0	0	0	0
Radius (occlusions)	9	9	9	9	9
Sigma space	9	9	9	9	9
Sigma color	25.5	25.5	25.5	25.5	25.5
Downsampling factor	1	2	2	1	2
	IMAG027	IMAG028	IMAG029	IMAG030	
Minimum disparity	-27	-19	-63	-31	
Maximum disparity	20	20	21	14	
Alpha	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	
Truncation (color)	30	30	30	30	
Truncation (gradient)	10	10	10	10	
Truncation (discontinuity)	10000	10000	10000	10000	
Iteration number	5	5	5	5	
Level number	5	5	5	5	
Data cost weight	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	
Disparity tolerance	0	0	0	0	
Radius (occlusions)	9	9	9	9	
Sigma space	9	9	9	9	
Sigma color	25.5	25.5	25.5	25.5	
Downsampling factor	1	1	2	1	

2.4 DMAG7

DMAG7 is an implementation of “Fast Bilateral-Space Stereo for Synthetic Defocus” by Barron et al. [2, 1, 10].

DMAG7 uses a “bilateral space”, a 5-dimensional grid (two dimensions for space and three dimensions for color), to group pixels into buckets (the grid cells). Each non-empty grid cell contains pixels that are close to each other in terms of space and color. How close depends on the grid size. Like all global methods, a functional which combines a data term and a smoothing term is minimized. The originality of DMAG7 is that this functional is minimized in bilateral space instead of pixel space, which leads to major speed improvements over methods that work at the pixel level. Once the solution is found in bilateral space, the pixels get their disparities from the grid cell they belong to.

In his paper, Barron uses the Birchfield-Tomasi technique [1] to figure out if a pixel in the left image matches a pixel in the right image. This in turn enables him to define a raw data matching cost that is very efficient (albeit probably not the best) because only two variables need to be stored per pixel: The minimum and maximum disparity for which there is a match. To avoid a lot of noise, two pixels are considered to be actually matching when all pixels within a patch match.

It should be noted that DMAG7 does not explicitly deal with occlusions unlike DMAG2, DMAG5, and DMAG6 which all compute a left and right depth map and perform the left-right consistency check to detect occlusions.

DMAG7 is quite fast if the grid size is not too large. It takes about 2 to 3 minutes to complete the depth map generation process for all the stereo pairs that were tested in this report. If the grid is made finer, the running time drastically increases.

Table 4 shows the parameters that were used to generate the depth maps. “Sample rate (spatial)” and “sample rate (color)” in the table correspond to σ_{xy} and σ_{rgb} in the paper. These sampling rates control the size of the “bilateral space” grid. The smaller the sample rate, the larger the grid. In his paper, Barron uses $\sigma_{xy} = 32$ and $\sigma_{rgb} = 8$ for all his results. Not to be contrarian, the same values were used here but these may not be optimal values. I used $\sigma_{xy} = 8$ and $\sigma_{rgb} = 32$ in [10] and thought the results were better than when using Barron’s recommended values. “Radius” controls the size of the pixel matching patch. The larger the “radius”, the larger the patch and the tighter the matching. “Lambda” is the weight given to the data cost in the functional that is minimized. The lower “lambda” is, the smoother the depth map is going to look like (at the expense of accuracy). In the paper, it is λ . “Max iterations” controls the number of iterations in the L-BFGS solver. “Hash table size” controls the number of buckets in the hash table used to build the “bilateral space”. The larger, the better. I use a hash table in my implementation but I am not sure what Barron use in his. “Epsilon” in the tables is the ϵ Barron describes as an offset to expand the bounds of the Birchfield-Tomasi technique when matching pixels. It is hard-coded at 4 in the paper but, in my implementation, it is a variable parameter. It is a rather crude way to cope with illumination or hue changes between left and right images.

Table 4: Parameters used with DMAG7

	IMAG0013	IMAG0017	IMAG0019	IMAG0020	IMAG0026
Minimum disparity	-20	-72	-23	-20	-59
Maximum disparity	17	14	62	22	55
Sample rate (spatial)	32	32	32	32	32
Sample rate (color)	8	8	8	8	8
Radius	12	12	12	12	12
Lambda	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Max iterations	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000
Hash table size	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000
Epsilon	8	8	8	8	8
	IMAG027	IMAG028	IMAG029	IMAG030	
Minimum disparity	-27	-19	-63	-31	
Maximum disparity	20	20	21	14	
Sample rate (spatial)	32	32	32	32	
Sample rate (color)	8	8	8	8	
Radius	12	12	12	12	
Lambda	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	
Max iterations	1000	1000	1000	1000	
Hash table size	10000	10000	10000	10000	
Epsilon	8	8	8	8	

3 The Game

The principle of the game is quite simple: For each stereo pair taken by the HTC Evo 3d, the two images are first rectified by ER9b [8] and then fed to each automatic depth map generator using the parameters given in tables 1, 2, 3, and 4. For a given depth map generator, the parameters are the same for all stereo pairs except for the “downsampling factor” in DMAG2 and DMAG6. Note that when downsampling the input images, any parameter that is spatial (like the support window radius in DMAG2) is also downsized by the same amount.

A total of 9 stereo pairs were used in this report. I believe they represent a good mix of real-life stereo pairs the average stereo photographer is likely to take. Some are of the classic stereo type where there is a bulky object close to the camera and a rather uneventful background behind. Those are usually easier to handle by an automatic depth map generator especially if the foreground object has good texture (a good example is a picture of flowers like IMAG0026). Others are more challenging because there are not so well defined objects at various depths and the 3d scene is deep (a good example is the row of bicycles in IMAG0019).

Instead of commenting on the obtained depth maps for each stereo pair and risking repeating myself, I defer my comments and conclusions to the next section.

3.1 IMAG0013

Figure 1 shows the rectified stereo pair that was given to all the depth map generators as input. Figure 2 shows the depth maps generated by the depth map generators.

Figure 1: Left and right images for stereo pair IMAG0013 after epipolar rectification by ER9b.

Figure 2: Depth maps generated (from left to right and top to bottom) by DMAG2, DMAG5, DMAG6, and DMAG7 for stereo pair IMAG0013.

3.2 IMAG0017

Figure 3 shows the rectified stereo pair that was given to all the depth map generators as input. Figure 4 shows the depth maps generated by the depth map generators.

Figure 3: Left and right images for stereo pair IMAG0017 after epipolar rectification by ER9b.

Figure 4: Depth maps generated (from left to right and top to bottom) by DMAG2, DMAG5, DMAG6, and DMAG7 for stereo pair IMAG0017.

3.3 IMAG0019

Figure 5 shows the rectified stereo pair that was given to all the depth map generators as input. Figure 6 shows the depth maps generated by the depth map generators.

Figure 5: Left and right images for stereo pair IMAG0019 after epipolar rectification by ER9b.

Figure 6: Depth maps generated (from left to right and top to bottom) by DMAG2, DMAG5, DMAG6, and DMAG7 for stereo pair IMAG0019.

3.4 IMAG0020

Figure 7 shows the rectified stereo pair that was given to all the depth map generators as input. Figure 8 shows the depth maps generated by the depth map generators.

Figure 7: Left and right images for stereo pair IMAG0020 after epipolar rectification by ER9b.

Figure 8: Depth maps generated (from left to right and top to bottom) by DMAG2, DMAG5, DMAG6, and DMAG7 for stereo pair IMAG0020.

3.5 IMAG0026

Figure 9 shows the rectified stereo pair that was given to all the depth map generators as input. Figure 10 shows the depth maps generated by the depth map generators.

Figure 9: Left and right images for stereo pair IMAG0026 after epipolar rectification by ER9b.

Figure 10: Depth maps generated (from left to right and top to bottom) by DMAG2, DMAG5, DMAG6, and DMAG7 for stereo pair IMAG0026.

3.6 IMAG0027

Figure 11 shows the rectified stereo pair that was given to all the depth map generators as input. Figure 12 shows the depth maps generated by the depth map generators.

Figure 11: Left and right images for stereo pair IMAG0027 after epipolar rectification by ER9b.

Figure 12: Depth maps generated (from left to right and top to bottom) by DMAG2, DMAG5, DMAG6, and DMAG7 for stereo pair IMAG0027.

3.7 IMAG0028

Figure 13 shows the rectified stereo pair that was given to all the depth map generators as input. Figure 14 shows the depth maps generated by the depth map generators.

Figure 13: Left and right images for stereo pair IMAG0028 after epipolar rectification by ER9b.

Figure 14: Depth maps generated (from left to right and top to bottom) by DMAG2, DMAG5, DMAG6, and DMAG7 for stereo pair IMAG0028.

3.8 IMAG0029

Figure 15 shows the rectified stereo pair that was given to all the depth map generators as input. Figure 16 shows the depth maps generated by the depth map generators.

Figure 15: Left and right images for stereo pair IMAG0029 after epipolar rectification by ER9b.

Figure 16: Depth maps generated (from left to right and top to bottom) by DMAG2, DMAG5, DMAG6, and DMAG7 for stereo pair IMAG0029.

3.9 IMAG0030

Figure 17 shows the rectified stereo pair that was given to all the depth map generators as input. Figure 18 shows the depth maps generated by the depth map generators.

Figure 17: Left and right images for stereo pair IMAG0030 after epipolar rectification by ER9b.

Figure 18: Depth maps generated (from left to right and top to bottom) by DMAG2, DMAG5, DMAG6, and DMAG7 for stereo pair IMAG0030.

4 The Post-Game

It is quite interesting to notice that DMAG2, DMAG5, and DMAG6 produce similar depth maps.

One would expect DMAG2 and DMAG5 to possibly deliver similar results because they are both local methods that use a bilateral filter (in the case of DMAG2) or an approximation of the bilateral filter (in the case of DMAG5) to smooth the raw data matching costs. The fact that we see similar results for DMAG2 and DMAG5 shows the power of the “guided filter” used in DMAG5 in lieu of the bilateral filter.

One would not expect a global method like DMAG6 to generate results similar to local methods (DMAG2 and DMAG5) but one has to acknowledge that it is indeed happening.

DMAG7 behaves completely differently from the others and the depth maps obtained by DMAG7 are quite different from the others (usually). The way the depth maps look can be easily explained by the methodology. Pixels that belong to the same grid cell get assigned the same disparity, which means that pixels within squares in the image get the same disparity if they are of similar color. This gives rise to a “ghosting” effect where one can kind of see details of the left image showing up in the depth map. If that disparity is correct, this a good thing and the results can look spectacular. If that disparity is wrong, this is a bad thing since the error may cover a large area depending on the size of the grid governed by the “sample rate (spatial)” and “sample rate (color)” parameters. The depth maps produced by DMAG7 are usually less accurate but probably more pleasing to see than those produced by the others, especially when the other depth map generators produce annoying outliers (due to low texture area).

It is my opinion that DMAG5 is the best “all-purpose” depth map generator as it usually produces good depth maps and is relatively fast (having a running speed independent of the kernel size helps a lot in that regard). Because DMAG2 and DMAG6 produce similar depth maps, there is no need to favor them over DMAG5. DMAG7 is the “oddball” as it can create superb depth maps in some cases but its accuracy comes into question (which may or may not be a problem depending on the application).

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